

Developing Language Competence in Military Personnel

Sotkulova Dildora Odinabekovna

Teacher of the Language Department of the Academy of the Armed Forces of
the Republic of Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT

Teaching a foreign language has been and remains an integral part of the process of forming a specialist with a higher education. Proficiency in at least one foreign language as a means of communication in socially conditioned areas of everyday life and professional activity is a mandatory component of the professional training of a modern specialist of any profile. Education at a university should provide for this a solid foundation of basic knowledge, skills and abilities in a foreign language speech-thinking, communicative activity and teach techniques and methods of independent work with a foreign language after graduation. The article deals with the issues based on developing language competence in military personnel and author tries to find solutions to the question based on the research.

Keywords: professional activity, communication, foreign language, language competence, military personnel, cadets.

INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of constant growth of educational information, an increase in the number of disciplines studied at a military university with stable terms of training of specialists, it becomes necessary to resolve the existing contradiction between the required quality of the language competence of future officers (according to the State Standard of Higher Education and the qualification

requirements for a university graduate) and the real possibilities of its formation with established traditional learning models.

According to the qualification requirements for the training of specialists in the currently widespread program of additional professional education in non-linguistic universities “Translator in. sphere of professional communication”, a graduate must master not only a certain set of basic lexical and grammatical structures of a foreign language, be able to recognize them and actively use them for communication purposes, but also acquire a certain set of special language skills, which is a conglomerate of knowledge in all areas chosen specialty in combination with a foreign language. The student must also know the features of functional styles, master all types of reading literature in the specialty, recognize the lexical and grammatical constructions inherent in the sublanguage of the specialty, and master the techniques of summarizing and annotating. Such a professionally-oriented language competence of a graduate of a non-linguistic university should be formed in a limited amount of study time allocated to learning a foreign language.

DISCUSSIONS

The practice of teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions shows that mastering a foreign language in a military university is compared with a civilian university in specific conditions, which affects the quality and efficiency of the educational process. The peculiarity of the training of military personnel (combining their training with the performance of official duties) determines the strict regulation of training time and the educational process itself. At the same time, the specificity of mastering a foreign language "from scratch" in a military university, in contrast to English or German, where the student's lexical and

grammatical base is laid down in secondary school, suggests a more intensive formation of the language competencies of cadets from the first training sessions.

One of the weak aspects of professional linguistic training of a graduate of a military university is his lexical skill. With the existing contradiction between the qualification requirements for the training of specialists (knowledge of about 5000 lexical units) and the study time allotted for these purposes, the formation of the lexical skill of students is carried out inefficiently. Testing of graduate cadets revealed that most of the vocabulary encountered in textbooks and studied by them in junior years, due to its low frequency and thematic value, is forgotten. There is also a problem between the ratio of the volumes of formation of the active and passive lexical vocabulary of the student. To expand the professionally oriented vocabulary of a graduate of a military university, the emphasis should be shifted towards a passive (receptive) dictionary, the words of which the graduate must understand when reading and listening to foreign speech.

The task of forming professional competencies (including professional linguistics) among military specialists in a short time without losing the quality of training involves the search for new ways to organize the educational process, the wider use of technical training aids, and the development of new educational technologies for the profile of training. We agree with the point of view of P.B.Lisov that one of the important directions for the successful implementation of linguistic professional training of cadets of military universities are: a rapid increase in the level of basic training of first-year cadets in foreign languages, the development of effective methods for highlighting the minimum content of educational material, necessary and sufficient for the formation of linguoprofessional competencies, the development of training technology based on their formation, increasing the efficiency of organizing independent work of

cadets¹. Interdisciplinary connections play an important role in teaching a foreign language and are closely interconnected with the life experience that students have at the time of training and which is formed in them in the process of mastering a specialty.

The educational process and its organization in modern higher education are aimed at the formation of a number of key competencies of a professional and general cultural nature. An analysis of the quality of knowledge of a foreign language by cadets of a military university shows that the level of knowledge and ability to apply them is low among the majority of cadets. At the moment, several contradictions can be distinguished: 1) between the acute need of modern society for professional military personnel, with a formed lexical competence at a high level, and their low actual availability; 2) between the need for well-planned work on the formation of lexical competence among cadets and insufficient knowledge of the issue of methods and means of effectively organizing the process of forming lexical competence for future military men.

The task of a foreign language teacher in the formation of lexical competence among cadets is to ensure that cadets, having a system of specific professional knowledge, skills and experience, can use them in the future as a basis for mastering and using professional vocabulary in all types of speech communication [2]. The purpose of the study is to develop pedagogical conditions for the formation of the lexical competence of cadets in foreign language classes at a military university. The work uses theoretical methods of analysis, generalization and systematization, comparison and generalization of information. This article provides a theoretical description of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of the lexical competence of cadets in foreign language classes at a military

university, the experimental verification of which was carried out on the basis of the Military Academy.

The formation of the lexical competence of cadets in the classroom in a foreign language puts consideration of the essence of the concepts of "formation" and "competence" as a priority stage.

In pedagogy, "formation" means a process associated with the use of means, methods of influencing the personality of students, to create in them a complex of specific skills and knowledge, a special way of thinking and a state of memory. In pedagogy, "formation" is considered as the result of human development, as the activity of a teacher in the implementation of upbringing and educational goals [3].

"Competence" is a multistructural concept, and scientists consider it in various aspects. Skill is understood as the ability to perform an action based on acquired knowledge and developed skills. Lexical skills are the ability to practice the formed lexical knowledge, freely operate with various lexical units and lexical combinations of words. The next element included in the structure of lexical competence is lexical skills. A skill in psychology is understood as an automated action that is formed in the course of an individual's speech activity.

The process of forming a lexical skill has the following stages:

- mastering the phonetic form of a lexical unit;
- performing an action to search and select a lexical unit;
- performing an action to combine lexical units;
- solution of speech problems [5].

The formation of a lexical skill is possible only with a close combination and implementation of all stages. Neglecting one of them can cause difficulties in the use of lexical units in communication. So, with the successful assimilation by cadets of the phonetic image of new lexical units, their free combination with each

other, their insufficient use in the process of solving speech problems causes difficulties with the use of learned lexical units in the communication process.

Taking into account the specifics of the content and methods of teaching the discipline, the process of forming the lexical competence of cadets in a foreign language class includes 4 stages.

At the first stage, cadets get acquainted with the new vocabulary, with its sound and visual forms, determine the relationship between the new lexical unit and its English-language meaning-translation. Cadets acquire the skills of recognizing new lexical units (lexemes) in given language contexts.

The second stage of the formation of lexical competence involves the formation and improvement of the skills of using acquired words with the formation of strong links between lexical units and their translation. The constant use of the acquired vocabulary at this stage with the integration of lexical units into various phrases can significantly strengthen the interlingual connection in the thinking and memory of students. At this stage, the most effective means for firmly fixing the meaning of lexical units (terms) will be the use and involvement of them in a large number of different phrases of a professional nature with already studied lexical units, which will not only activate the previously accumulated vocabulary, but also successfully assimilate this recently material.

The third stage of formation is related to the further integration of a foreign language lexical unit already as part of a phrase to the next stage of assimilation - use in various professionally oriented sentences. When a trainee-cadet has already developed a very specific image and structure of a lexical unit and he can easily operate the received lexical units in phrases of various levels of complexity and number of words, the next step, in our opinion, will be the gradual introduction of phrases into sentences for expansion the student has a picture of using the acquired

knowledge and skills in different language units. Successful mastery of vocabulary at this stage will not only allow the student to improve their knowledge, but will also provide an opportunity to expand and develop their linguistic horizons.

The fourth stage of the assimilation of lexical units and the formation of lexical competence is important because we are approaching the main goal, for the solution of which the above three levels were described - the use of acquired lexical units in a given communicative or speech situation. This can be a translation of a vocational test in a specialty, a monologue statement on some given topic, dialogic speech, etc. At this stage, students must show their acquired knowledge and skills in using foreign language lexical units for the successful and effective solution of professional communication tasks, which will require students to use previously acquired speech experience and learned speech means [6]. This stage of competence formation is aimed at performing practical communicative tasks, taking into account the specifics of a professional military technical foreign language, different situations and circumstances of communication, and requires the speaker to use formed speech knowledge, skills and abilities at a high professional level.

In this case, the question arises of defining common problems and, on the basis of existing knowledge, combining the vision of the problem and possible options for solving it in a foreign language. Since the achievement of successful learning outcomes, including a foreign language, depends to a decisive extent on the direction, degree of independence, manifestation of creative abilities and internal activity of students, the nature of their activities, then these factors should serve as an important criterion for choosing the method that the teacher achieves in the process of learning the tasks assigned to them. Taking into account and application by the teacher of higher education of such aspects of teaching as the

life experience of students, immersion in the techno-linguistic environment, the use of interdisciplinary connections, is aimed at enhancing the language training of future military specialists.

In our opinion, one of the most promising areas in solving the problem of successful linguoprofessional training of cadets in military universities is the specification of the content of education, followed by the development of new educational technologies that involve the optimization of the educational process as a specific psychological and pedagogical concept of education, are guided by the final result. At the same time, the analysis of materials that determine the content of foreign language training, including the requirements of state educational standards, indicates the need for its concretization and focus on the professional specifics of training a graduate of a military university.

This, as a rule, is due to the fact that the selection and formation of the volume of the lexical content of training, textbooks and teaching aids in various military universities continues to be carried out only on the basis of the teachers' subjective idea of the purpose of the training course, without using methods that increase the objectivity of the selection and optimize the volume of assimilated in the process of learning vocabulary.

The reason for this, until now, has been the great difficulty in self-selection by a teacher in the conditions of a continuous educational process of a higher educational institution of a scientifically based, necessary and sufficient lexical minimum for the formation of linguistic professional competence of a graduate of a certain specialty. However, the increasing introduction of new information technologies and software into the educational process of universities solves this problem. This is evidenced by studies in this direction that have appeared in the last decade.

CONCLUSION

In the course of the study, the essence of improving the teaching of a foreign language to cadets of military universities based on the optimization of the lexical component, which is the process of mastering professionally significant foreign language lexical units, providing the formation of the necessary level of knowledge, skills and abilities in the use of a foreign language in professional activities, is substantiated in the cadets. The structure of this process is determined, which includes a number of stages: organizational, diagnostic, lexical optimization, communicative and activity, control and evaluation. The content of this process is disclosed, which consists in the achievement by its subjects in the course of their activities of the set goals and objectives, which are expressed in the formation and development of knowledge, skills and abilities among cadets sufficient for the practical use of a foreign language in accordance with the requirements of the State Educational Standard of Higher Professional Education and military specialty.

References:

1. Abansky Yu.K. Optimization of the learning process (General didactic aspect). -M.: Pedagogy, 1977.
2. Drummers A.V., Deryugin N.I. Military pedagogical diagnostics. - M., 1995.
3. Beloshitsky A. V. Differentiated training of cadets of a military university as a factor in the professional development of military specialists: dis. . cand. ped. Sciences: 13.00.08. Voronezh, 2004.
4. Bim I.L. Methods of teaching foreign languages as a science and problems of a school textbook. - M., 1977. 288 p.
5. Verbitsky A.A., Bakshaeva H.A. Development of cadets' motivation in contextual learning. Monograph. M., 2000.
6. Davydova M.A. Activity method of teaching foreign languages: Scientific and theoretical guide. -M.: Higher school, 1990.
7. Denisova L.G. The place of intensive methodology in the system of teaching a foreign language in secondary school // Foreign Languages at School. M., 1995. - No. 4.